

Solvent Effect on Infrared Spectra

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Infrared spectra, both fundamental and overtones of N-H band, of aniline, methylaniline, diphenylamine, and indole have been studied in structurally different solvents. The validity of the K.B.M. equation has been tested in the case of indole, using the binary solvent CS_2 - benzene. The observed shifts, both blue and red, are explained in terms of intermolecular hydrogen bonding and localised electrostatic interactions which are related with the polarisability of the solvent molecules.

A large volume of work has been done on the effect of solvent on infrared spectra of molecules, especially containing ketonic, hydroxy, and amino groups. The properties of the solvents were correlated to changes in the properties of the solute. Recently Price *et al.*¹ reviewed the effect of environment and the change of state on spectra. It has been found out that the solvent effect on group frequencies can be studied conveniently by plotting the frequency difference, $\Delta \bar{\nu}$, of the one solute in a series of solvents, against similar data under identical experimental conditions for some other frequency. Kirkwood² and Bauer and Magat³ have deduced an expression (K.B.M. equation) for the change in vibrational frequency of a dipole caused by the change in energy due to the electrostatic interaction between the medium and the dipole. The relative frequency shift is given by

$$\frac{\Delta \gamma}{\gamma} = -C \frac{\epsilon - 1}{2\epsilon + 1}$$

where C is a constant and ϵ is the dielectric constant of the medium. In the frequency region used for the determination of spectra, one can assume $\epsilon \approx n^2$;

$$\frac{\Delta \gamma}{\gamma} = -C' \frac{n^2 - 1}{2n^2 + 1}$$

where n is the refractive index of the medium. The constant C' depends on the molecular model.

Kirkwood's theory was applied first to the bands of hydrochloric acid at 2855 and 5555 cm^{-1} . The theory holds good except in carbon disulphide and for pure liquid⁴. Jones and Badger⁵ studied the effect of the dielectric constant on the infrared spectra of methanol. They have studied the third harmonic of the O-H frequency; K.B.M. equation holds good only for data in non-polar liquids. The relative frequency shift in chlorinated solvents is lower, but those in aromatic solvents are higher than the calculated value from the dielectric

1. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1960, A255, 5.
2. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, 2, 351.
3. *J. Phys. Radium*, 1939, 9, 319.
4. West and Edwards, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 14.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3132.

function. Similar results are observed in methanol and other alcohols and in phenol. The infrared spectra of N—H vibration in pyrrole were studied by Linnell⁷, Tomimoko⁸, and Fuson and Josien⁹. The K.B.M. equation in polar and aromatic solvents was explained as due to hydrogen bonding and molecular complexes. Recently Bellamy *et al.*¹⁰ reviewed the literature on the solvent effect on infrared spectra and pointed out the importance of the polarisation of the bond under consideration due to the other groups present in the same molecule. In the study of the solvent effect on N—H stretching mode of pyrrole¹¹, it was found convenient to plot the relative frequency shifts, $\Delta \bar{\nu}/\bar{\nu}$, of one solute in a series of solvents against the corresponding values under the same experimental conditions of some other bond, X—H. According to the present authors, these observations will be true only when the different types of intermolecular forces and liquid structure play identical role in changing the group frequencies under consideration. The electron density on nitrogen atom, calculated by the method of molecular orbitals for aniline, diphenylamine, and triphenylamine by Berthier and Pallman¹², is in agreement with resonance theory of Wheeland¹³, whereas calculated values for pyrrole, indole, and carbazole¹⁴ are completely different from those based on the resonance theory. Previously, the hydrogen bonding, in which the N—H is taking part, was considered doubtful, probably due to its weak nature⁵. In pyrrole and indole, with increasing concentration, the sharp N—H bands fade out and a broader band due to lower frequency appears. The extinction coefficients of unassociated N—H frequency for pyrrole, indole, and carbazole were found to be about four times more than those for aniline and diphenylamine. The frequency shift due to solvent was large for pyrrole, indole, and carbazole in benzene, whereas for aniline and diphenylamine, the shift was small. Similar to Mecke's study¹⁶ for phenol, Fuson and Josien⁹ calculated the percentage of monomeric molecules. The association for amino compounds is generally less than those for phenols. The separation between the free and the associated band maxima increases with acidity. In the study of the solvent effect on C = O stretching, Bellamy and Williams¹⁷ observed an interesting result regarding the application of solvent effect to the systematic study of the Fermi resonance. The importance of the specific interaction over the overall effect given by K.B.M. equation, shown by Bellamy and others, was found to be true also in hydrogen-bonded systems. According to Bellamy's views¹⁸ not much solvent shifts in X—H bonds, which have already taken part in

6. Searles *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3704; 1953, **75**, 71; Tamres, *ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 3375; Tomimoko, *Soumen Kemist.*, 1950, **B23**, 44; Stuart, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 1115; Lutke and Mecke, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1949, **53**, 241; Josien and Lascombe, *J. Acad. Sci., Paris*, 1954, **238**, 2414; Dodd and Stephenson, "Hydrogen Bonding Ljubljana, Aug. 1957" edited by Hadzi and Thompson, Pergamon Press, London, 1959, p. 177.
7. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 179.
8. *Ibid.*, 1952, **20**, 1054.
9. *Ibid.*, 1954, **22**, 1169.
10. *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1958, **13**, 60; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1960, **A225**, 23.
11. Bellamy *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **54**, 1120; Bellamy, "Proceedings of the Conference on Molecular Spectroscopy, London, Feb. 1958, ed. by Thornton & Thompson, Pergamon Press, London, 1959, p. 216.
12. *Compt. rend.*, 1948, **226**, 1725.
13. "The theory of Resonance", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1944, 167.
14. Longuet-Higgins and Coulson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, **43**, 87.
15. Sutherland, *ibid.*, 1940, **38**, 880.
16. *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, **9**, 161.
17. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, **55**, 14.
18. Bellamy and Hallam, *ibid.*, 1950, **55**, 220.

inter- or intra-molecular bonding, were expected. Recently Allerhand and Schleyer¹⁶, however, have found that $\lambda_{OH \dots O}$ are very sensitive to environment.

For the study of the validity of the K. B. M. equation, related solvents should be used as the liquid structure plays an important role in the solvent effect. In a similar study, Mukhodkar¹⁷ reviewed the effect of Lorentz factor on optical activity. The validity of the K. B. M. equation, which corrects the effect of the refractive index of the medium, the latter being one of the factors affecting the molecular property, can be studied by using a binary solvent, hexane-carbon disulphide, where the refractive index varies from 1.3828 to 1.6216. In the present work, the solvent effect on infrared spectra of aniline, methylaniline, diphenylamine, and indole has been studied in a variety of solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Infrared spectra of aniline, methylaniline, indole, and diphenylamine in different solvents were determined on a Beckman IR 4 spectrophotometer, using lithium fluoride interchange. Overtones were studied on a Beckman Ratio Recording DK 2 spectrophotometer. Matched quartz cells, which were transparent up to 2500 cm^{-1} , were used. For concentrated solutions 0.1 mm cells with sodium chloride windows were used in infrared region and variable path cell was used for near I.R. region. Spectra were taken at different concentrations. Solutions were prepared by weight in stoppered conical flasks. Spectra were taken for conditions under which the sensitivity and resolution were maximum.

TABLE I

Solvents.	Aniline ($c = 1.0M$).		Methylaniline ($c = 0.9M$).		Diphenylamine ($c = 0.9M$).		Indole ($c = 0.6M$).			
	$\bar{\nu}_1$.	$\Delta\bar{\nu}_1$.	$\bar{\nu}_a$.	$\Delta\bar{\nu}_a$.	$\bar{\nu}_1$.	$\Delta\bar{\nu}_1$.	$\bar{\nu}_1$.	$\Delta\bar{\nu}_1$.		
1. Acetone	3425	-21	3346	-18	3376	-32	3428	-47	3439	-116
2. Dioxane	3419	-27	3338	-26	3366	-42	3299	-76	3493	-152
3. Methylene chloride	3429	-17	3355	-9	3401	-7	3479	+4	3537	-18
4. Ethylene chloride	3430	-16	3355	-9	3399	-10	3470	-5	3541	-14
5. Carbon disulphide	3438	-8	3259	-5	3400	-8	3477	+2	..	..
6. Chloroform	3423	-23	3350	-14	3411	+3	3488	+13	3545	-10
7. Tetrachloroethylene	..	..	..	..	3410	+2	3490	+15	3552	-3
8. Tetrachloroethane	3422	-24	3350	-14	..	..	3482	+7	3537	18
9. Carbon tetrachloride	3440	-6	3359	-5	3407	-1	3438	-37	3554	-1
10. Ethyl acetate	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	3470	-85
11. Benzene	3434	12	3356	8	3385	-13	3462	-13	3520	-85
12. Chlorobenzene	3438	-8	3359	-5	3400	-8	3468	-7	3541	-14
13. Bromobenzene	3425	-11	3357	-7	3398	-14	3467	-8	3530	-25
14. Nitrobenzene	3438	-8	3358	-6	3398	-10	3459	-16	3515	-40
15. Anisole	3433	-13	3354	-10	3398	-10	3453	-22	3501	-54
16. Pentachloroethane	3440	-6	3361	-3	3408	0	3486	+11	..	..
17. Trichloroethylene	3439	-7	3359	-5	3408	0	..	..	..	..
Cyclohexane	3446	0	3364	0	3408	0	3475	0	3555	0
Literature	3481*	..	3395*	..	3430**	..	3433†	..	3491‡	..

* Buswell *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 61, 3252.** Fuson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, 20, 145.† Richards and Burton, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1949, 45, 874.19. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 371.20. *J. Poona Univ.*, 1960, 18, 41.

TABLE II

Solvents.	Aniline ($c = 1.0M$).				Methylaniline ($c = 0.9M$).		Diphenylamine ($c = 0.9M$).		Indole ($c = 0.6M$).	
	$\bar{\gamma}_3$.	$\Delta\bar{\gamma}_3$.	$\bar{\gamma}_4$.	$\Delta\bar{\gamma}_4$.	$\bar{\gamma}_2$.	$\Delta\bar{\gamma}_2$.	$\bar{\gamma}_1$.	$\Delta\bar{\gamma}_1$.	$\bar{\gamma}_s$.	$\Delta\bar{\gamma}_s$.
1. Acetone	6650	-18	6844	-34	6662	-20	7138	-86	7215	-176
2. Dioxane	6642	-26	6820	-58	6662	-20	7161	-63	7246	-145
3. Methylene chloride	6648	-22	6849	-29	6706	+24	7219	-6	7353	-39
4. Ethylene chloride	6646	-22	6835	-43	6682	0	7218	-6	7337	-54
5. Carbon disulphide	6646	-22	6849	-20	6687	+5	7218	-6	7348	-43
6. Chloroform	6650	-18	6859	-19	6692	+10	7235	+11	7375	-18
7. Tetrachloroethylene	..	..	..	..	..	..	7235	+11	7375	-18
8. Tetrachloroethane	..	..	..	..	6701	+19	7224	0	7358	-39
9. Carbon tetrachloride	6654	-14	6854	-24	6706	+24	7240	+16	7391	0
10. Ethyl acetate	..	..	..	..	..	..	7177	-47	7257	-134
11. Benzene	6654	-14	6854	24	6673	-9	7196	-28	7315	-76
12. Chlorobenzene	6659	-9	6854	-24	6697	+15	7202	-22	7337	-54
13. Bromobenzene	6650	-18	6844	-34	6682	-20	7188	-36	7326	-65
14. Nitrobenzene	6659	-9	6849	-29	6673	-9	7202	-22	7326	-65
15. Anisole	6654	-14	6854	-24	6687	-15	7194	-30	7331	-60
16. Pentachloroethane	..	..	..	..	6714	+32	7235	+11	..	..
17. Trichloroethylene	6657	-11	6859	-19	6711	+29	..	..	..	..
Cyclohexane	6668	0	6878	0	6682	6	7224	0	7391	0

The K. B. M. equation is derived, assuming a point dipole surrounded by a continuous dielectric. Specific interactions and liquid structure have not been taken into consideration. If the assumptions made in the K. B. M. equation were correct, the plot of $\Delta\gamma/(\bar{n}^2-1)/(2\bar{n}^2+1)$ vs. n_D must be a straight line in structurally related systems. Results for indole in CS_2 -hexane²¹ are shown in Fig. 1. It is observed that there is a slight but observable curvature for K. B. M. plot; a good straight line is obtained when $\Delta\gamma/(\bar{n}^2+2)^{1/3}$ is plotted against n_D . Therefore the equation which corrects for the refractive index is given by

$$\Delta\gamma = C \times \frac{\bar{n}^2 + 2}{3}$$

That indole-nitrobenzene- CS_2 system does not provide a straight line, does not mean that $(\bar{n}^2+2)^{1/3}$ is not the correcting factor for the general field effect. Lorentz factor contributes only a small fraction to the total solvent effect.

When a similar type of intermolecular interactions is prevailing, a uniform curve will be obtained for the K. B. M. equation instead of a straight line, as in the case of indole-carbon disulphide-nitrobenzene. The voluminous literature data show, however, well-scattered points for K. B. M. plot and it is really beyond statistical skill to draw some curve through the points. The failure of the K. B. M. equation is in the explanation of blue shift instead of the invariable 'red shift', predicted by the K. B. M. equation. La Lau²² explained the blue shifts for Y-OH vibrations of aromatic hydrocarbon on the basis of localised electrostatic interactions.

21. Proceedings of the Conference on Molecular Spectroscopy, London, Feb, 1958, edited by Thornton and Thompson, Pergamon Press, London, 1959, p. 205.

In the present work, the fundamental bands and the overtones of N—H vibrations have been studied to obtain an insight into the local interactions in these systems. The results are recorded in Tables I and II.

FIG. 1. Effect of refractive index factor on spectra.

○ Indole in hexane—CS₂.
 ,, nitrobenzene—CS₂.

the solutes giving rise to large intermolecular interactions between solute molecules. The band at low frequency is due to N—H . . . N bonding. The strong interaction of halo compounds and amines is shown by the formation of a solid compound photolytically when dry carbon tetrachloride and dry aniline are mixed and exposed to light.

For amino compounds, intermolecular hydrogen bonding between solute molecules occurs in concentrated solutions. In solvents having high polarisable groups, the free N—H will form hydrogen bonding with the solvent molecules, showing a corresponding change in the frequency. The shift in frequency will be qualitatively related to the strength of the hydrogen bonding. There will be corresponding change also in their intensity and band width. The data are related to electron displacements in the solvent molecule, as suggested by Ingold's ideas and Wheland's theory of resonance. Cyclohexane is considered to be an inert solvent; CCl₄ is not an ideal solvent, as the overall dipole moment of a molecule is not

Indole shows a very strong band at 3550 cm⁻¹ in carbon disulphide (1.9 mg./5 ml CS₂), whereas in concentrated solutions (200 mg./5 ml CS₂) in addition to a strong band at 3550 cm⁻¹, a weak but sharp band at 3490 cm⁻¹ is also observed. In hexane these two bands are of equal intensity. Only one band at 3515 cm⁻¹ is, however, observed in nitrobenzene. These observations can be explained on the basis of N—H . . . N bonding in concentrated solutions in inert solvents like hexane or CS₂. Intensity of the bands show that CS₂ is not an ideal inert solvent; in fact, due to the high polarity of the C—S bond, an abnormal behaviour is expected, as shown in physical properties like spectra, dipole moment, optical rotation, etc. In nitrobenzene solvent-solute interactions also predominate, giving rise to comparatively broad band. For diphenylamine and methyl aniline, the N—H bands are resolved for the first time into two branches; the resolution is due to the efficient optical alignment of the spectrophotometer, the inert solvent cyclohexane, and high concentration of the

the deciding factor for the environmental conditions affecting molecular properties. Bond moments are to be considered. Methylaniline shows both blue and red shifts in different solvents when compared to that in cyclohexane. From the table, the solvents can be divided into two groups : (1) solvents containing oxygen and (2) solvents containing halogen. N-H stretching frequencies in solvents containing oxygen show red shift, whereas in solvents containing halogen show a blue shift. Anisole, benzene, and toluene behave similarly as cyclohexane. The maximum blueshift is in chloroform, whereas maximum red shift is in dioxane and acetone. In fact, for such comparison, the data in the vapour phase are advisable. One cannot compare, however, the data determined with the literature values available in gaseous phase as the two sets of values may not be determined under the same experimental conditions, especially the calibration of the optical system.

For chlorine the +M effect is vanishingly small as compared to -I effect, but for oxygen both are comparable. Shift in N-H bonding frequency is very small. For aniline all solvents show red shift only. For indole, oxygen-containing solvents show large shifts as compared to halo-solvents. In benzene also, a comparatively large shift is observed both for fundamental and harmonic band. Diphenylamine behaves like methylaniline; it shows, on the whole, a red shift in oxygen-containing solvents and a blue shift in halo-solvents for the fundamental and harmonics.

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